

SUGGESTIONS FOR IMPROVING MANAGEMENT ACTIVITY

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STUDY OF THE EFFICIENCY OF BIOLOGICAL TREATMENT TECHNOLOGY OF DOMESTIC COMMUNAL WASTEWATER USING AQUATIC PLANTS. (TASHKENT REGION AS AN EXAMPLE OF WASTEWATER TREATMENT INSTALLATION OF BEKOBAD CITY)

Ismailkhodjaev B.Sh - National Research University "Tashkent Institute of Irrigation and Agricultural Mechanization Engineers", Doctor of Biological Sciences, professor, department "Ecology and water resources management", 100000, Tashkent, Qori Niyoziy. 39, Uzbekistan

Nasibov B.R. - phd student. National Research University "Tashkent Institute of Irrigation and Agricultural Mechanization Engineers" bobnasibov@gmail.com

Kholmiraeva B.A. - Peoples' Friendship University named after academician A. Khatbekov, candidate of biological sciences, associate professor, department of "Chemistry and biology", 100067, Shymkent, Tole bi st. 32, Kazakhstan

Muminova SH.S – J.Tashenov University, Department Chemistry, Biology. Phd Senior Lecturer. Shymkent, Kazakhstan

Abduraimova N.Sh - J.Tashenov University, Department Chemistry, Biology. senior teacher. Shymkent, Kazakhstan

***Аннотация.** The results of the analysis carried out in "Bekabad City Wastewater Treatment Plant" show that all indicators of the chemical analysis at the first sampled point (wastewater entered) were found to be higher than those of the samples taken from the other 3 points. In accordance with the tasks set before us according to the plan of our scientific work, we chose the conditions of cultivation favorable for the optimal development of aquatic plants and continued the experiments. The results showed that all the domestic municipal wastewater collected in "Bekobod City Wastewater Treatment Plant" originates from multi-story houses located in Bekobod city and is ultimately discharged to "Bekobod City Wastewater Treatment Plant" through main pipes. An average of 2328.7 m³ of wastewater is collected in "Bekabad City Wastewater Treatment Facility" during the day. According to the information received from Bekobod City "Suv Wastewater Unitary Enterprise DUK", "Bekobod City Wastewater Treatment Facility" produces an average of 849,975.5 m³ of wastewater per year. The amount of municipal wastewater collected in the facility was 272,240 m³ (36%) in the summer season of the year. The results of the analysis conducted at the "Bekabad City Wastewater*

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Treatment Facility" show that all indicators of the chemical analysis at the first sampling point (where the wastewater entered) it was found that it was higher than the sample values obtained from the remaining 3 points. In accordance with the tasks set before us according to the plan of our scientific work, we chose the conditions of cultivation favorable for the optimal development of aquatic plants and continued the experiments.

Keywords. Domestic-communal wastewater, volume, quantity, biological treatment technology, laboratory analysis, treatment methods.

Кириш.

It is known that 2/3 of our planet consists of water, but only 0.2% of it is fresh water. Therefore, it is considered the most important mineral necessary for the existence of organisms in the water-terrestrial sphere, and it is known to everyone that it is an important and invaluable natural resource for mankind. In our republic, it is necessary to regularly monitor the status of industrial, domestic and communal wastewater, and strictly monitor it in accordance with the list of industrial enterprises included in the program of monitoring natural environment polluting sources. Today, the amount of toxic substances in the waste water of industrial enterprises is increasing more and more. The mineral salts and carbon dioxide gas contained in the wastewater are consumed by algae growing in the water, and the wastewater is cleaned of various impurities. The use of this method is effective in the treatment of waste water of industrial enterprises and household utility facilities [1-4].

Taking into account that the protection of water sources and the rational use of these resources is an important issue, a wide range of measures for nature protection, including the rational use of water resources, are being implemented in Uzbekistan. In addition, today, new, cost-effective technologies, introduction of a closed cycle of water use, creation of ecologically safe, economically cheap and effective methods of biological treatment of waste water are the demand of the time [5-7].

Among the sources of pollution of water resources, the most important place is occupied by waste water from industry and household-utility. Industrial waste water contains various acids, phenols, hydrogen sulfate, ammonia, copper, zinc, mercury, cyanide, arsenic, chromium, and other toxic substances, oil, petroleum products, which are dangerous for living organisms, and they, together with the wastewater used in industrial enterprises, enter the river, polluting lakes and reservoirs [8-11].

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According to the above information, it is clear that extensive scientific research has been carried out on wastewater treatment, but the formation, amount, seasonal distribution and treatment methods of domestic municipal wastewater have been little studied, and in this regard, it is necessary to accelerate the biological treatment process and increase the level of treatment. Not enough research has been conducted. The increase in the number of people on earth and the influence of the amount of toxic substances in the wastewater added from various enterprises on the concentration of wastewater are considered to be the main factors of the shortage of clean water [12-15]. Taking into account the above-mentioned current problems, we planned to conduct scientific research on the amount of waste water formed in the city of Bekobod, Tashkent region, the concentration of waste water, the amount of substances from the composition of waste water, depending on the seasons [16-19].

We have chosen the Bekobod city wastewater treatment plant as the main object for conducting scientific research [20-21]. Bekobod city wastewater treatment plant is located in Bekobod district of Tashkent region, its total area is 12.47 hectares. Most of the structure is located between the Syrdarya River and the Dostlik Canal.

The total amount of domestic municipal wastewater collected in the Bekobod City Wastewater Treatment Plant is discharged from the multi-story buildings located in the Bekobod City through the main pipes to the Bekobod City Wastewater Treatment Plant. An average of 2328.7 m³ of wastewater is collected in the Bekobod city wastewater treatment plant during the day. According to the information received from the Bekobod City Water and Wastewater Unitary Enterprise DUK, an average of 849,975.5 m³ of wastewater is formed in the Bekobod City Wastewater Treatment Plant. The amount of collected domestic communal wastewater is distributed according to the seasons: 272240 m³ (36%) in the summer season, 190185 m³ (21%) in the autumn season, 178175 m³ (18%) in the winter season, and 209120m³ (25%) in the spring season. falls (Fig. 1). It can be seen that in the summer months, the volume of water used by the population for domestic purposes increases, and as a result, this leads to an increase in the amount of wastewater.

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Diagram 1. Seasonal distribution volume of wastewater flowing into the Bekobod city wastewater treatment plant (%).

The analysis of the quality result of domestic municipal wastewater of Bekobod city wastewater treatment plant by the State Unitary Enterprise "Suvsoz" in 2020 is described (Table 1).

Table 1
Chemical indicators of waste water entering Bekobod city wastewater treatment plant by seasons

Indicators	Spring	summer	Autumn	Winter
The smell	4	5	4	3
Color	3.3	3.5	3.4	3.2
pH	8,3	8.9	8.5	8.2
dissolved oxygen, mg.O ₂ /л	6,5	7,89	5.5	5
KBC ₅ , мг O ₂ /L (Biological consumption of oxygen ₅)	70.8	80.7	75.4	65.2

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Phosphates, mg/l	2,68	3.25	2.02	2
Copper, mg/l	3,7	4.2	3,9	3.2
Ammonia, mg/l	3,8	4.2	4.0	3.2
Iron, mg/l	4.5	5.1	4.9	4.1
Chlorides, mg/l	43,9	51,5	48,9	38,0
Chrome, mg/l.	0,49	0,89	0,55	0,47
Sulfates, mg/l.	164,8	175.2	169.2	160.0
Nitrates, mg/l.	67.2	72.5	69.5	65.2
nitrites,mg/l.	4,2	5.6	4.9	4.1

As can be seen from the table above, it is known from the results of the laboratory of the State unitary enterprise "Suvsoz" of Bekobod city that the chemical composition of the wastewater coming out of the facility changes depending on the seasons. Therefore, the amount of chemicals in wastewater increases in the summer months of the year, that is, due to the high water needs of the population, and it is observed that it is relatively lower in the spring and autumn months. Depending on the seasons, it was found that the volume and composition of the wastewater collected in the Bekobod city sewage treatment plant is high in terms of physical and chemical properties, the main reason for this process is the increase in the number

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of high-rise buildings and the population.

After going through the mechanical devices of the wastewater treatment method in the Bekobod city wastewater treatment plant, the harmful substances in the wastewater have been significantly reduced. Of these, iron decreased by 1.5 times, suspended matter by 4 times, sulfate by 25%, chloride and nitrogen by 30-40%, BOD indicator decreased by 60%. The physical and chemical composition of the wastewater collected in the facility changes depending on the season, and experiments have shown that the amount of pollutants in the facility is the highest in summer, and their amount is relatively low in spring. After the wastewater treatment process, it was found that the basic substances in the wastewater in the facility decreased by 25% (up to 4 times). In the conducted experiments, it was observed that some chemicals (nitrate and nitrite nitrogen) were purified in very small quantities. The results of experiments carried out at the facility show that the

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quality of wastewater does not meet the requirements of GOST, and this situation requires the development of a scientific basis for improving the technology of wastewater treatment.

Waste water entering the treatment station of the Bekobod city wastewater treatment plant is 2328-2450 m³/day.

Bekobod City Wastewater Treatment Plant: the grate plant is mechanically cleaned by hand 2 and 3 times a day, the air tank is cleaned once a month, the primary clarifier is cleaned once every 15 days, and the sand trap is cleaned once a month. Based on the conducted scientific research plan, we have chosen the conditions for growing aquatic plants that are favorable for optimal development in order to fulfill the tasks set before us. The analysis of the literature showed that several different biological water plants were grown in laboratory conditions at

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different concentrations of wastewater, and as a result, their participation in the treatment of domestic and communal wastewater was studied. In our scientific research, before the experiment in the Bekobad city wastewater treatment plant, we determined the points where wastewater samples were taken from different parts of the wastewater treatment plant, and then we took samples and conducted analyzes.

(Table 2) Physico-chemical parameters of waste water from Bekobad city wastewater treatment plant before the experiment

Chemical indicators	From the waste water lifting pipe of the "BShSOT" facility	From the entrance to the air tank of the "BShSOT" facility	From the entrance to the air tank of the "BShSOT" facility	Waste water coming out of "BShSOT" facility
The smell	5	4,4	3,2	2,5
Color	3,5	3,1	2,5	2,2
pH	8,9	8,5	8	7,8
dissolved oxygen, mg.O ₂ /л	7,89	7,2	8,5	9,2
КБС5, мг O ₂ /L (Biological consumption of oxygen 5)	80,7	78,75	60,1	45,7
Phosphates, mg/l	3,25	2,99	2,51	1,85
Copper, mg/l	4,2	3,55	2,95	2,2
Ammonia, mg/l	4,2	3,91	3,25	2,55
Iron, mg/l	5,1	4,55	4,2	3,45
Chlorides, mg/l	51,5	45,59	39,57	35
Chrome, mg/l.	0,89	0,44	0,38	0,36
Sulfates, mg/l.	175,2	150,8	113,8	102,3
Nitrates, mg/l.	72,5	65,2	52,4	42,2
The smell	5,6	4,95	4,09	3,55

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The results of the analysis carried out at the Bekobod city wastewater treatment plant showed that all indicators of the chemical analysis at the first sampling point (where the wastewater entered) were higher than the indicators of the remaining 3 samples, that is, the wastewater has not yet passed through any treatment devices. After further cleaning procedures, we can observe that the indicators have significantly decreased in the last step and the cleaning level has reached 50-60%. In accordance with the tasks set before us according to the plan of our scientific work, we have chosen conditions for growing aquatic plants that are favorable for their optimal development. During the analysis of the literature, we studied the growth of pistia and eichhornia plants in laboratory conditions at different concentrations of wastewater and their participation in the processes of purification from various substances. In order to evaluate the efficiency of biological treatment of wastewater with the participation of the Pistia plant at the Bekobod city wastewater treatment plant station, before the experiment, wastewater samples were taken from 4 points of the treatment plant at a depth of 10 cm from the water surface to determine the chemical composition of the wastewater. During the experiment, two samples were taken from the waste water formed in the facility, that is, before and after pistachio plant cultivation, water samples were taken, and their chemical analysis was carried out.

From the laboratory results, we can see that the chemical composition of water before pistachio plant cultivation and in the first days of plant cultivation is almost the same. Because in the initial period of pistachio plant cultivation in wastewater, i.e. during the first 20-25 days, the plant is in the stage of adaptation to the chemicals contained in the water. The indicator at points 1-2 (65-70%) before the aquatic plant is grown and after the adaptation process, that is, the chemical substances contained in the wastewater accumulate in the root system of the plant, and when the chemical

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composition of the wastewater formed in the structure at points 3-4 after the purification process is studied, their degree of purity is 90 We can see that -95 %.

2-жадвал

Physico-chemical characteristics of wastewater from the Bebod wastewater treatment plant before and after the experiment.

Chemical indicators	BShSOTI from the sewage pipeline	Before the experiment		From experience after	Regulations
		From Aerotank wastewater at the outlet	BShOSTI coming out Waste water	After the pistachio plant is grown	
The smell	5,0	3,0	2,5	1.0	2,0
Color	3.5	2,2	1,89	1.2	2
pH	8.9	8,2	7,9	7.1	6-8
dissolved oxygen, mg.O2/л	80.7	44,1	39,3	7.0	30
KBC5, мг O2/L (Biological consumption of oxygen 5)	3,25	1,95	1,65	0,95	1,02
Phosphates, mg/l	3,45	2,22	2,75	1,05	2,0
Copper, mg/l	4,01	2,95	2,65	1,85	3,95
Ammonia, mg/l	0,35	0,45	0,35	0,12	0,1
Iron, mg/l	3.25	2.95	2,45	0.65	2.5
Chlorides, mg/l	51,5	47,2	43,0	10,2	350,0
Chrome, mg/l.	175.2	148,1	110,0	34.04	350
Sulfates, mg/l.	72.5	55,4	48,7	7.5	45
Nitrates, mg/l.	5.6	4,1	3,8	0.95	3,3

In this table, comparing the physico-chemical indicators of wastewater before the experiment with the indicator at the entry and exit points of the facility, the

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wastewater was purified by 60-65%, and after the experiment, when the pistachio plant was grown, we can see that the wastewater in the aerotanks was purified by 90-95%. The results of this experiment showed that when the wastewater of the Bekobod wastewater treatment plant is treated biologically with the help of aquatic plants, depending on the type of plant, it was determined that there is a possibility of purifying the wastewater from 90% to 95%.

Summary

When we analyzed the wastewater coming to the Bekobod city wastewater treatment plant in the laboratory, the results showed that the amount of substances in the wastewater varies in different seasons depending on the season. It was observed that the amount of substances in the water was at a minimum level in the winter season, while it was found that their amount increased relatively in the spring and autumn seasons. And in the summer season, we can observe that their amount has reached the maximum level. It was found that 40-70% of the pollutants contained in the wastewater were absorbed by the pistachio plant in the 5-7 days of the experiment using biological methods of the pistachio plant, and the oxygen demand was satisfied by 90-92%, and the purification efficiency was 95%.

On the basis of these results, it is possible to introduce biological methods of wastewater treatment with aquatic plants of Bekobod city wastewater treatment plant. Similar technologies can be used in the processes of wastewater treatment in all cities and residential areas of our Republic.

REFERENCES

1. Spina, F., Anastasi, A. E., Prigione, V. P., Tigrini, V., & Varese, G. (2012). Biological treatment of industrial wastewaters: a fungal approach. *Chemical Engineering Transactions*, 27, 175-180.

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AMERICAN JOURNAL

<http://sasfimaindex.is-great.org/>

ISSN: 6577-9665

Impact Factor: 7.5

2. Shah, M. P. (Ed.). (2021). *Biological Treatment of Industrial Wastewater* (Vol. 5). Royal Society of Chemistry.
3. Gupta, R., & Singh, R. L. (2019). *Advances in biological treatment of industrial waste water and their recycling for a sustainable future* (pp. 225-66). R. L. Singh, & R. P. Singh (Eds.). Singapore: Springer.
4. Abduqodirova, M., & Ismoilkhodjayev, B. (2021). Treatment of polluted municipal wastewater in Tashkent. In *E3S Web of Conferences* (Vol. 264, p. 01052). EDP Sciences.
5. Abdukadirova, M. N., & Sh, I. B. (2023). Evaluation of the effectiveness of the technology of biological treatment of wastewater at the Salar aeration station. *Texas Journal of Agriculture and Biological Sciences*, 15, 121-126.
6. Ismailhodjaev, B., Kuvatbekova, K., Kholmiraeva, B., Boburbek, N., Mirzaqubulov, J., Eskaraev, N., & Abduraimova, N. (2022). Activity, patterns, and localization of carbonic acid enzymes in algae used in wastewater treatment. *Texas Journal of Engineering and Technology*, 14, 11-17.
7. Sh, I. B., Karamat, K. P., Xalmirzayeva, B. A., Nasibov, B. R., & Israilov, I. X. (2023). Effect of " RIZOKOM-1" and " SERHOSIL" biopreparations on soil moisture in cotton development. *Texas Journal of Agriculture and Biological Sciences*, 15, 116-120.
8. Ismailhodjaev, B., Mirzaqubulov, J., Kholmiraeva, B., Kuvatbekova, K., Eskaraev, N., & Abduraimova, N. (2022, June). Comparative study of the activity and localization of carbonic anhydrase in some microalgae and their dependence on the concentration of carbon dioxide and nitrogen supply. In *AIP Conference Proceedings* (Vol. 2432, No. 1). AIP Publishing.
9. Mehrzad, M., Behpour, M., & Kashi, F. J. (2023). Novel environmental method for enhanced biodegradation of contaminated wastewater via immobilizing nanoparticles on a new bacterial strain isolated industrial textile. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 325, 116528.
10. Abdukadirova, M. N., & Sh, I. B. (2023). Evaluation of the effectiveness of the technology of biological treatment of wastewater at the Salar aeration station. *Texas Journal of Agriculture and Biological Sciences*, 15, 121-126.
11. Daud, N. M., Abdullah, S. R. S., Hasan, H. A., & Dhokhikah, Y. (2022). Integrated physical-biological treatment system for batik industry wastewater: A review on process selection. *Science of The Total Environment*, 819, 152931.
12. Guieysse, B., & Norvill, Z. N. (2014). Sequential chemical–biological processes for the treatment of industrial wastewaters: review of recent progresses and critical assessment. *Journal of hazardous materials*, 267, 142-152.
13. Sh, I. B., & Abdukadirova, M. N. (2019). Assessment of the effectiveness of biological treatment of wastewater at the " Binokor" aeration station located in Orta Chirchik district of Tashkent region. *Journal of Irrigation and Reclamation*, (1), 15.
14. Egamberdiev, N. B., & Abdukadirova, M. N. (2018). Scientific and practical basis of biological treatment of wastewater. *A gro ilm journal*, (2), 52.

SUGGESTIONS FOR IMPROVING MANAGEMENT ACTIVITY

AMERICAN JOURNAL

<http://sasfimaindex.is-great.org/>

ISSN: 6577-9665

Impact Factor: 7.5

15. Sh, I. B., & Nasibov, B. R. (2022). Influence of algae on fur growth, development, physiological condition and fur quality. *Texas Journal of Agriculture and Biological Sciences*, 5, 67-70.
16. Egamberdiev, N. B., Sharipjonova, Z., Nasibov, B., Khomidov, A. O., Alimova, M. I., & Abdumalikov, A. A. (2021). Biological treatment of industrial and domestic wastewater of a brewery in Uzbekistan. In *E3S Web of Conferences* (Vol. 264, p. 01055). EDP Sciences.
17. Sharipkhojayevich, I. B., Abdusalom o'g'li, K. H., Rustamjon o'g'li, N. B., & Abbasovna, Y. C. (2023). Mechanisms for Capturing Particles From Vehicles From The Side of Ornamental Tree Leaves And Their Effect On The Amount Of Pigment In The Leaves. *Texas Journal of Agriculture and Biological Sciences*, 15, 127-133.
18. Nasibov, B. R., Boliyeva, I. A., & Abduqodirova, K. B. (2022). MONITORING THE DECLINE OF PLANTS AND TREES IN ANDIJAN AND VALLEY REGIONS THROUGH ARTIFICIAL ROAD IMAGES, DETERMINING THE CHANGES IN GROUNDWATER CONDITIONS WITH THE HELP OF GIS TECHNOLOGIES. *Talqin va tadqiqotlar ilmiy-uslubiy jurnali*, 3(4), 202-213.
19. Nazarov, K., SHarofiddinov, R. S., Bolliyeva, I. A., & To'xtayeva, M. X. (2023). SUV RESURSLARIDAN FOYDALANISHNING HUQUQIY ASOSLARI. Молодые ученые, 1(19), 25-29.
20. Nasibov, B. R., & Abdullaev, B. D. (2023). IMPACT OF CLIMATE CHANGE ON GROUNDWATER RESOURCES. *Ethiopian International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*, 10(11), 441-449.
21. Abdukadirova, M. N. (2022). DEVELOP STUDENTS'PRONUNCIATION SKILLS FOR HEARING IMPAIRED. *Экономика и социум*, (3-1 (94)), 7-9.